

ISic0323

I.Sicily inscription 0323

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Estella Kessler,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus) S(acrum)

2. L(ucius) Arrius

3. Secundus

4. vix(it) an(nos) XVII

5. marmorariimarmorari

6. convive(ntes) fecer(unt)

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation (en)

Sacred to the shades of the underworld. Lucius Arrius Secundus lived for 17 years. The stonemakers living with him made this.

Translation (de)

Den Seelen der Unterwelt gewidmet. Lucius Arrius Secundus lebte für 17 Jahre. Die Steinmacher, die mit ihm leben, haben das gemacht.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491532

EDCS 21900361

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7039 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650758>)

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